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The Prevalence of Intestinal Helminths in Comprehensive High School, Ilese-Ijebu, Ogun State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Intestinal parasitic infections are a public health concern in tropical countries, such as Nigeria. The infection is associated with complications such as retarded growth, low cognition, gastrointestinal obstruction, etc. A total of 100 samples were collected from Students attending Comprehensive High School, Ilese-Ijebu in Ogun State, Nigeria, between January to February 2022 for Intestinal Helminthes using the direct wet preparation method. The results of the study showed that out of 74 (74%) female -students' stool examined 22 (29%) students had intestinal helminths and, the 26 male (s) students accounted for 9 (34%), making a total of 31% students were being infected. The parasites' distribution was thus as follows: *Ascaris lumbricoides* was 48%; Hookworm 17%; *Strongyloides stercoralis* 13%; *Taenia* species 22% respectively. The result of this shows that parasitic infection exists among secondary school students in Nigeria. Therefore personal hygiene, regular deworming, eating washed fresh fruits and regular health education are recommended.

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INTRODUCTION

Infestation by intestinal helminths is a major public health problem which causes chronic inflammatory disorders such as chronic anaemia, growth stunting, protein-calorie malnutrition, fatigue, poor cognitive performance, reduced long-term survival, diminished physical fitness and school attendance in school-age children^{1, 2}. The most common intestinal parasites within the group of helminths are STHs, including *Ascaris lumbricoides* (roundworm), *Necator americanus* and *Ancylostoma duodenale* (hookworm), and *Trichuris trichiura* (whipworm), have been considered to infect over a thousandth of million people, and much more are at risk of infections^{3, 4, 5}. In tropical and sub-tropical nations many situations caused the observed high prevalence of intestinal parasites, such as climatic conditions, poor sanitation, a lack of safe water and inadequate modern toilet facilities⁶. And, some cultural behaviours may influence exposure to infection with specific pathogens; for example, eating raw fruits with food-borne parasites, and also working barefoot on the farm can lead to hookworm infection^{7, 8}. World Health Organization pointed out that more than a quarter of a million preschool children and over half a billion school-going children reside where the parasitic infection is common and immediate interventions are necessary⁹. The prevalence and distribution of intestinal helminths vary from place to place in any population¹⁰. Hence, this cross-sectional survey is to study the Prevalence of Intestinal Helminths in Comprehensive High Schools, in Ilese- Ijebu, Ogun State, Nigeria.

METHODS

Study area

The project work was carried out at Comprehensive High School. Ilese- Ijebu. Ilcse- Ijebu, Ijebu- Ode, Ogun State. Ilese- Ijebu is a town founded after Ijebu- Ode along the old Benin Expressway. Ogun State College of Health Technology can be used to locate the town Ilese- Ijebu. Ilese Ijebu is under Atan town, the headquarters of Ijebu North-East Local Government in Ogun Slate. Nigeria. It has an estimated population of 10. 000 according to the 2006 population census. The predominant occupation is farming and trading. The borehole is their source of water.

Materials

Sterile Universal bottles, Applicator sticks, Microscope slides, Coverslip, Normal saline, Lugol's Iodine and Microscope. 2.3 Sample collection Well-labelled Sterile Universal bottles were given to Fifty (50) students of Comprehensive High School, Ilese- Ijebu to put about 5gm of stool they defecated. 2.4 Sample analysis Macroscopic and microscopic examinations of stool were done to reveal intestinal parasites in the stool sample collected following the standard operating procedures (SOPs) as recommended by the WHO¹¹.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study showed that out of 74 (74%) female -students' stool examined 22 (29%) students had intestinal helminths and, the 26 male (s) students accounted for 9 (34%), making a total of 31%) students were being infected. The

parasites' distribution was thus as follows: *Strongyloides stercoralis* (Threadworm) 13%;
Ascaris lumbricoides (round worm) was 48%;
Ancylostoma duodenale (Hookworm) 17%;
Taenia species (tapeworm) 22% respectively.

TABLE 1: Age of participants selected for intestinal helminthes

Age (Years)	Number Examined	Number of Infected	% Infected	Number not Infected	% Not Infected
11-12	44	10	22.73	34	77.27
13-14	28	10	35.71	18	64.29
15-16	17	7	41.18	10	58.82
17-18	11	4	36.36	7	63.64
Total	100	31		69	

Table 2: Sex of participants selected for intestinal helminths Infection

Age (year)	MALE			FEMALE			TOTAL	
	No examined	No infected	% Infected	No examined	No infected	% Infected	Total Infected	% Infected
11-12	8	3	33.33	36	7	31.82	10	32.26
13-14	7	3	33.33	21	7	31.82	10	32.26
15-16	6	2	22.22	11	5	22.73	7	22.58
17-18	5	1	11.11	6	3	13.63	4	12.90
Total	26	9	99.99	74	22	100.00	31	100.00

Table 3: The distribution of helminths on participants

Age (year)	<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	Hooworm	<i>Strongyloides stercoralis</i>	<i>Taenia</i> species
11-12	4	2	2	2
13-14	5	2	2	1
15-16	4	1	1	1
17-18	2	0	0	2
Total	15	5	5	6

DISCUSSION

From the results obtained 31% prevalence of intestinal parasite (helminth) infection among students of Comprehensive High School, Ilese-Ijebu was recorded which was higher than that

recorded from a Previous study in Babile town of overall prevalence of intestinal helminthiasis to 27.2%¹⁰. In Ethiopia, the prevalence of *Ascaris lumbricoides* infection was relatively high across different regions. 29% in the mountains, 35% in

the cool areas and 38% in the lowlands. The prevalence of hookworm infection was highest in the lowlands (24%) followed by the temperate (15%) and highlands (7%). The notable differences in the studies are explained by changings in geography, socio-economic conditions, and cultural practices of the population under consideration. Conclusion Results show there was a high prevalence 31% of intestinal parasite (helminth) infection among students of Comprehensive High School, Ilese-Ijebu which was due to not deworming at least ones in every three months, washing raw vegetables properly before eating and adopting personal hygiene and community hygiene.

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